

THE IMPORTANCE OF SEED AND COMMERCIAL GRAIN STORAGE METHODS

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Annotatsiya: Dala ekinlarining hosildorligi va mahsulotning sifati ekish uchun ishlatiladigan urug‘ning urug‘lik sifatlariga bog‘liqdir. Urug‘ tirik organizm hisoblanib, uning murtagidan kelgusida o‘simlik rivojlanadi. Shuning uchun urug‘lik bo‘lajak o‘simlikning biologiyasi, xo‘jalik va nav xususiyatlarini o‘zida mujassamlashtirgan bo‘ladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Kuzgi bug‘doy, urug‘lik material, saqlash usullari, kritik namlik, kimyoviy konservalash, zararli patogen zararlanishlar.

Аннотация: От качества семян, использованных для посева, зависит урожайность полевых культур и качество продукции. Семя считается живым организмом, а из его стебля развивается растение. Следовательно, семя воплощает в себе биологические, хозяйственные и сортовые особенности будущего растения.

Ключевые слова: Озимая пшеница, семенной материал, способы хранения, критическая влажность, химическая консервация, вредные патогенные повреждения.

Annotation: The yield of field crops and the quality of the product depend on the quality of the seed used for planting. A seed is considered a living organism, and a plant will develop from its stem. Therefore, the seed embodies the biology, economic and variety characteristics of the future plant.

Key words: Winter wheat, seed material, storage methods, critical moisture, chemical preservation, harmful pathogenic damage.

In the history of agriculture, much attention was paid to the quality characteristics of seeds. Seed quality is one of the most important factors affecting yield. GOST requirements are used when analyzing product quality. GOST requirements are also applied when storing and processing agricultural products, especially when processing and storing seed wheat. State standard of Uzbekistan (UzDst 2823:2014) for processing, storage and transportation of wheat grain, taking into account the requirements of the state standard [1; No. 05-542] is carried out based on the requirements.

After receiving the seeds collected from the field, they are sorted by variety, reproduction and batch. In this process, the seeds are cleaned of foreign matter and various impurities. It is not enough to study the individual characteristics of groups in order to maintain the quality of seeds and commercial grain in elevators and warehouses for a long time without loss of dry mass. For this reason, it is appropriate to study the complex systematic effect of all organizational parts. According to the theory of grain storage, grain mass should be stored in the following modes.

1. Maintaining the grain mass in a dry state, i.e. maintaining its humidity to critical levels.
2. Preserving the grain mass in a cold state, that is, limiting the vital activity of living groups.
3. Storage of grain mass in sealed conditions (without exposure to air).

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, grain storage modes are much more useful than storing grain in a dry state. The mode of storing grain in a dry state reduces the need for water of living organisms, mites and pests, and microorganisms in the grain mass in the fall. When the amount of free water in the grain is lost, the needs of living groups are not satisfied and this leads to their death. Therefore, when storing grain in a dry state, the moisture content should not exceed a critical moisture level. Critical humidity is moisture that limits the vital activity of microorganisms, mites and pests

in the grain mass, as well as the speed of physiological processes in the grain. The critical moisture content for grain grain is 12-14%. Experiments show that well-cleaned, undamaged grain batches can be stored dry in elevators for 2-3 years, and in warehouses for up to 5 years.

The importance of keeping the grain mass cold plays an important role in the mid-latitudes of the MDH territory, as well as in the northern regions of Uzbekistan.

Refrigerated warehouses are divided into 2 groups:

- 1) storage of grain mass at a temperature of 0-10°C;
- 2) storage of grain mass at temperatures below 0°C.

Methods for cooling grain mass:

Passive cooling. In this case, the air exchange process is carried out by opening the doors and windows of warehouses.

Active cooling. This cooling is carried out by moving grain from one place to another using conveyors in grain cleaning machines.

For long-term storage of grain mass at high humidity, it is necessary to exclude exposure to air. For this purpose, grain is stored in sealed conditions. There are 3 ways to create an oxygen-free environment in a grain storage facility.

1. Increasing the amount of CO₂.
2. Creating a vacuum.
3. Filling the voids in the grain mass with the help of various chemical gases.

Storing grain mass in sealed conditions is used for grain intended for soft feed. It is forbidden to store seeds intended for baking in an airtight manner.

Currently, the method of chemical preservation of grain mass is also used for storing seeds and commercial grain. This method has several advantages over existing storage methods, such as efficiency, low consumption and low power consumption.

Chemical preservation of grain mass is carried out in the following cases:

1. This method is used for long-term storage of grain mass with low moisture content. Karbofos is used for this. The chemical used does not affect the nutritional and edible properties of the grain and helps to destroy mites and pests in it.

2. To store grain mass with a high moisture content, use a 1-1.2% solution of sodium pyrosulfite salt. In this case, it is advisable to use formic, fatty, propionic, acetic acids, ammonium carbonate salts, ozone, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_3$, NH_3 -ammonia from organic acids.

In industry, grain mass can be completely sterilized using X-ray, infrared, and ultraviolet rays. For example, 1 million. Grain mass irradiated with an x-ray dose, with a moisture content of less than 16%, can be stored for 3 months. The grain mass irradiated with these doses with a moisture content of 20-25% can be stored for several days. After this, the development of fungi is observed. 2.5 million, the respiration rate of corn (dry) grain irradiated with an x-ray dose decreased by 2.9 times. [2; 64 p].

For high-quality grain storage, granaries are subject to various technical (construction, fire, etc.), technological, operational and economic requirements. All these requirements are aimed at preserving grain products during storage with minimal damage without deteriorating their quality. Any granary must be strong enough. That is, its walls and floor must withstand the pressure exerted by the mass of grain and maintain their structure even in unfavorable atmospheric conditions. Precipitation and groundwater in the grain mass have bad consequences. One of the main requirements for storing grain is that the presence of seeping water, rodents, birds, as well as harmful insects and ticks is strictly prohibited. Granaries should be convenient for gasification and degassing, as well as disinfestation. Granaries must have devices designed to carry out dust protection measures. Currently, stone, brick, reinforced concrete and metal granaries are used in our country.

CONCLUSION

1. Maintaining the grain mass in a dry state, i.e. reducing its moisture content to a critical moisture level, limits physiological processes in grain batches. In particular, cases of self-heating of grain masses are prevented.

2. Grain collected from fields may contain living organisms such as mosquitoes, grain-sucking lice and weevils. These living organisms cause some damage to the

quality of grain during storage and reduce the quality of the grain. Storing the grain mass in a cold state limits the life activity of living groups.

3. In the course of research, the method of chemical preservation of grain mass has a number of advantages in terms of quality and long-term storage of winter wheat seed material. This method uses chemicals to kill mites and pests in grain batches. Chemicals do not affect the nutritional and nutritional properties of the grain.

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